

PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL SOCIAL REQUIREMENTS FOR TEACHERS

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Annotation This article discusses the social requirements for the pedagogical profession and their importance in the educational process.

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Pedagogical activity as a whole system consists of the following components:

- The pedagogical personality has a humanistic orientation, its interests, values and ideals are focused on the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation;
- Excellent knowledge of specialty subjects, teaching methods, pedagogical psychology;
- pedagogical ability (communication skills, diligence, ability to imagine the future, professional independence, rapid comprehension of sensory information (reading from the face));
- mastering pedagogical techniques, ie self-management, interaction and collaboration.

Another feature of the personal qualities of teaching includes a wide range of knowledge about children, their psychology, about the school, the organization of educational processes and its content, methods. This knowledge forms the general pedagogical culture, if the teacher, the educator does not master this culture, he will never be a true master of his work, will not go beyond the bad, old way, using ready-made templates in one mold.

However, the modern culture is not enough for a modern teacher - special knowledge and skills - the ability to observe children, identify important things in their development, identify ways and means of their development, in-depth analysis of various interactions, scientific systematization of pedagogical research and achievements will be required.

Thus, a teacher can achieve his personal and professional qualities at the following stages:

1. In-depth study of pedagogical and psychological sciences.
2. In-depth knowledge of special disciplines, methods of teaching them.
3. Active participation in pedagogical practice and its effective implementation.
4. Constantly analyze your activities and be critical of them.
5. Independent work on themselves, study in advanced training courses.

The specificity of the pedagogical purpose can be seen in the following:

1. The requirements for the personality of the teacher are determined by society, that is, the results of pedagogical activity are related to the interests of society. His work is aimed at the full development of the personality of young people. Pedagogical activity ensures the social coherence (sequence) of the generation. It transmits the experience of one generation to the next, realizing the natural potential of man to gain social experience.

3. The personality of the teacher is regularly associated with the management of the personal activities of students. It is important that the pedagogical goal becomes the goal of the student. The educator must have a clear idea of the purpose of his activity and ways to achieve it, and be able to explain to them that achieving this goal is also important for students. As Goethe put it: "Speak with conviction, and then the word and the deception of the audience will come naturally."

Management of student activities in the pedagogical (educational) process is complicated because the goal of the teacher is always focused on the future of the student. Realizing this, skilled educators design the logic of their activities in accordance with the needs of students. This is the essence of collaborative pedagogy.

Thus, the specificity of the purpose of the educator's personality requires the teacher to:

- full understanding of the social functions of society and acceptance of their identity. The "growth" of the goals of society, its transformation into a pedagogical point of view;
- creative approach to certain actions and tasks;
- to take into account the interests of students, to turn them into the goals of pedagogical activity.

The uniqueness of the teacher's personality is manifested in the following.

1. Man is not an inanimate object of nature, but a uniquely active being who has his own characteristics, his own perception of events, and his own evaluation of them. As noted in psychology, each person is unique. He is a participant in the pedagogical process with his own goals, passions and personal behavior.

2. The educator works with a person who is constantly evolving. It is not possible to use the same stereotyped behaviors in approaching them. This requires a constant search for creativity from the educator.

In addition to educators, students are influenced by the environment, parents, other science teachers, the media and social life. Therefore, the pedagogical work involves simultaneously correcting the total effects and the ideas that arise in the students themselves.

Only a person who can always have a positive-moral impact on a student's personality is a true educator. To achieve this, the educator must constantly improve his moral qualities.

Involvement of students in activities such as cocktails, communication, play, reading is a key tool of education. Every skilled educator should have their own individual pedagogical system.

Some educators, in order to master the secrets of professional mastery, first of all strive to improve teaching methods. This is natural, because it is through the methods that the educator engages his students in a variety of learning activities. At

the same time, motivation of students to learn is influenced by factors other than the educational methods, techniques and tasks chosen by the teacher. The success of a teacher's work depends in many ways on his personality, character, and interaction with students. Usually the impact of these on the educational process seems insignificant. But an experienced educator will pay attention to how his behavior affects students, making the necessary corrections and improving it. Therefore, pedagogical mastery should be considered as a set of personal qualities of a teacher, and it should be borne in mind that it is associated with a teacher with a high level of psychological and pedagogical training.

References

1. Podlasyy I.P. Pedagogy. New course. T.1.-M .: VLADAS, 1999, 235 p.
2. Gonobolin F.N. A story about a teacher. - T .: 1967, page 66.
3. Pedagogy: Ucheb. posobie dlya studentov ped. institutes / Pod red. Yu.K. Babanskogo. - M: Prosveshchenie, 1983, p.600.
4. Kuranov M., Muranov B In the professional profile of the teacher of the National program - "People's education", 1998, issue 1, pages 42-45)